

Buehler Farms Project, Sandusky County

Since construction in 2021, the nutrient retention and hydrologic regime of the Buehler Farms Project have been unclear. Soils at this Project have capacity to sorb phosphate, suggesting potential for retention of any received phosphorus loads. However, researchers have not been informed when, or if, the property owner pumps water into the wetland from the ditch despite multiple requests for this information. If the Project is not pumping from the inflow ditch, or during low flow conditions, then there is a missed opportunity to capture nutrients before flowing into Muddy Creek and Sandusky Bay.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is actively managed. The Project has 40 acres of restored wetland, consisting of a coastal diked wetland pool that receives water from a ditch adjacent to the pool through a control structure. The ditch appears to be a mix of tile drain runoff from adjacent agricultural fields and is connected to Little Muddy Creek through culverts under the road. There are two water control structures at this Project, one is near the intake pump and the other connects to Little Muddy Creek. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an event when water is let into or out of the site through a water level control structure.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar coastal diked wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- If pumping occurred from the ditch during conditions with increased nutrient levels and was then held in the Project pool before entering Sandusky Bay, the Project could have a greater impact on nutrient reduction.

Lack of information about pumped inputs limits the understanding that can be gained from this Project. As a result, the Monitoring Program does not plan to collect new data at this Project in 2025.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.